

Effect of frequency of cultivation on density of *Rottboellia cochinchinensis* and all weed species. IRRI, Aug 1983-Jul 1985.

total weed density. *Cyperus rotundus* L. populations decreased in plots that were frequently cultivated but increased with less frequent cultivation. Densities of *Eleusine indica* (L.) Gaertn. and *Portulaca oleracea* L. also increased.

Total weed density after 2 yr was not reduced in the plots rototilled every 5 wk. However, *R. cochinchinensis* was replaced by less competitive weeds. □

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Weed control in irrigated wet and dry seeded rice in medium-textured soils of Northwestern India

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Eight weed control treatments were tested to control weeds in direct seeded rice when sprouted seeds were sown on a puddled field and when dry seeds were sown on an unpuddled bed. The trial was in a split-plot design with three replications during 1983 and 1984 monsoon seasons.

The field was well-drained sandy clay loam soil. Pusa 33, 105-110 d duration and photoperiod insensitive with high yield potential, was the test variety. The crop received 100-22-42 kg NPK/ha.

Preemergence herbicides like oxadiazon, pendimethalin, and butachlor were applied 4-5 d after seeding (DAS); propanil was applied 21 DAS.

Echinochloa colona and *E. crus-galli*

Effect of herbicide schedule and seeding method on grain yield of direct seeded rice. IARI, New Delhi, India, 1983-84.

Treatment ^a	Grain yield (t/ha)		Weed wt (g/m ²)	
	Dry seeded	Wet seeded	Dry seeded	Wet seeded
Oxadiazon 0.6 pre + propanil 2 post	4.3	4.7	19	20
Oxadiazon 0.6 kg pre	4.1	4.6	18	19
Hand weeding + propanil 2 post	3.8	3.9	36	36
Pendimethalin 1.5 pre + propanil 2 post	2.1	3.0	71	61
Butachlor 1.0 pre + propanil 2 post	1.9	2.2	73	69
Pendimethalin 1.5 pre	1.4	2.5	88	73
Butachlor 1.0 pre	0.9	2.0	101	81
Weedy check	0.5	1.3	125	105
CD for weed control treatment means for the same method of seeding	0.3		6	
CD for method of seeding means for the same level of weed control	0.3		6	

^aPre and post = preemergence and postemergence applications. Herbicide measurements are in kg ai/ha.

were the predominant weed flora.

Among the preemergence herbicides, oxadiazon at 0.6 kg ai/ha resulted in the best weed kill, with yields of 4.1 t dry seeded rice and 4.6 t wet seeded rice/ha

(see table). Combining propanil at 2 kg ai/ha with butachlor or pendimethalin was more effective than when the preemergence herbicides were applied alone. □